

A Dual-Discriminator GAN for Sleep EEG Signal Synthesis

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Abstract: The interpretation of one's overnight sleep process based on EEG signal is of importance for the inspection and treatment of various sleep-related disorders. The automatic sleep staging models have benefits as the assistant computerized tools to release the clinicians from the laborious task of manual sleep stage scoring. However, the issues of data insufficient and class imbalance are common for clinical data. The data problem is crucial to be solved when applying the automatic sleep staging models for real clinics. In this research, the network architecture of GAN (Generative Adversarial Network) is investigated by using one generator and two discriminators for the synthesis task of sleep EEG signals. The data augmentation performance by the dual-discriminator GAN and the sleep stage classification performance by combining with a typical machine learning classifier are evaluated on the sleep recording of subjects. The obtained results showed that the constructed dual-discriminator GAN is effective to generate samples which are closer to the time and frequency characteristics of real sleep EEG signal. It would be a useful method to solve the data problems for the training and optimization of automatic sleep stage classifiers in the field of sleep staging.

Keywords: Generative adversarial network; Electroencephalograph; Data augmentation; Sleep staging; Dual-discriminator

I. INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a fundamental physiological state that manifests as a temporary loss of autonomic awareness and plays a key role in the maintenance of homeostasis, immune system, energy metabolism, cognitive function and neuronal plasticity [1]. However, with the rapid development in the field of industry, business, economy, etc., more and more people are suffering by sleep problems due to the influence of hard work pressure, poor and irregular living style. Long-term sleep problems will lead to a series of sleep disorders such as insomnia, and will also induce the other psychological, neurological or cardiovascular disorders. The diagnosis and treatment of sleep disorders have become increasingly important. The interpretation of one's overnight sleep into the change of various sleep stages is one of the evaluation ways for the diagnosis and treatment, where different sleep stage indicating the light or deep state of sleep.

According to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) manual [2], the overnight sleep process consisted of several sleep cycles which is categorized into five stages: Wake (W), Non-REM Stage 1 (N1), Non-REM Stage 2 (N2), Non-REM Stage 3 (N3) and Rapid Eye Movement (REM). The inspection of sleep stages required qualified skill and adequate clinical experience. The visual inspection of sleep stage is based on the recording of neurophysiological signals through the measurement of polysomnography (PSG). The PSG measurement includes electroencephalogram (EEG), electrocardiogram (ECG), electromyogram (EMG), electrooculogram (EOG), pulse rate, oxygen saturation and respiration, etc. The total recording time would be 7-8 hours. The visual inspection may take 1-2 hours. Additionally, the inspection should be done by two clinicians to ensure more accurate interpretation. The visual inspection is a hard and laborious task.

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Fig. 1 Sleep stages during one's overnight sleep process

There had been various automatic classification methods developed by using machine learning and deep learning techniques. The automatic sleep staging models have benefits as the assistant computerized tools to release the clinicians from the hard and laborious task of manual sleep stage scoring. The literatures published in recent years showed quite good performance according to the experiments implemented on several kinds of public data sets. However, satisfied results had not been obtained when applying the methods on the real clinical sleep recordings. One of the main problems is of data [3] [4]. The acquisition of sleep recording and credible labeling of sleep stages are both not easy which cause the amount of real clinical data for the training of classification models are less. On the other hand, the duration of different sleep stage during one's overnight sleep is imbalanced. For example, N2 accounting for about 30% to 50% while N1 is often less than 10%. The ratio of the amount of N2 and N1 will near to 5:1. The above issues of data insufficient and class imbalance are common for sleep recording. Since most of the classification methods required large amount of training data with high-quality labels, as well as a relatively balanced distribution of samples belonging to different categories. The data problem is inevitably affected the classification performance of automatic methods when dealing with real clinical sleep recordings.

Among various techniques for data problem, the data augmentation (DA) is an effective way to address the issues of insufficient data and imbalanced classes. Generative adversarial network (GAN), as a typical generative model, has demonstrated powerful capabilities in the field of image generation since it was proposed. In recent years, GAN and its improved models have been researched in the field of EEG data augmentation. Hartmann et al. [5] proposed a model to synthesize EEG based on GAN named EEG-GAN in 2018. The synthesized samples possessed quite satisfied

performance in metrics such as IS (Inception Score), which opened a new path to the DA of EEG. Zhou et al. [6] implemented DA of EEG by combining GAN with Gaussian white noise of different intensities, which effectively alleviated the class imbalance problem in automatic sleep staging. Xu et al. [7] and Guan et al. [8] used Wasserstein GAN (WGAN) to synthesize the multi-channel EEG signals in the pre-seizure phase, and experimentally demonstrated that the false-positive rate of epilepsy prediction could be reduced by DA. LEE et al. [9] proposed an EEG synthesis model called SIGGAN by combining the contextual information of the missing segments, which effectively solves the problem of missing segments due to equipment failure, etc. Experiments have proved that the EEG generated by SIGGAN is not only close to the real one, but also retains the auxiliary information such as sleep stages.

By investigating the existing literatures on EEG data augmentation, it is found that most of the current models are focused on the time-sequential characteristics of EEG. Accordingly, the designed methods are mainly from the perspective of the time domain. In fact, the sleep stages are interpreted mainly based on the characteristics of certain frequency components, including the changes of δ activity (0.5-4 Hz), α activity (8-13 Hz), β activity (14-25 Hz) in EEG, etc. Therefore, the information in the frequency domain deserves greater attention for EEG. When compared to the amplitude and waveform characteristics of EEG signals in the time domain, the distribution characteristics in the frequency domain are more important and helpful for the interpretation of sleep stages. The problem of synthetic samples that tend to be realistic in the time domain but may be distorted in the frequency domain had been reported in the field of 2D images [10] [11]. However, the related problem still lacks sufficient attention in the field of EEG signal augmentation.

In this study, the structure of generative adversarial network model is investigated by dual-discriminator for sleep EEG augmentation. One discriminator is based on real neural network for the time series of EEG, while another is based on complex neural network for the power spectrum of EEG. The visual inspection and multi-metric quantification are used to comprehensively assess the quality of synthetic EEG signals. The sleep EEG recorded from real clinics is utilized to evaluate the effectiveness of presented method. Additionally, the generated samples are adopted for the training of a machine learning model. The classification performance before and after data augmentation is tested.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Theoretical foundations for GAN

GAN [12] is an unsupervised machine learning architecture that consists of two parts: generator and discriminator. The goal of the discriminator is to try to discriminate the true samples as true and the generated samples as false, i.e. to maximize the loss function shown in equation (1):

$$\mathcal{L}_D = \mathbb{E}_{x_r \sim P_{data}(x)} [\log D(x_r)] + \mathbb{E}_{x_G \sim P_G(x)} [\log (1 - D(x_G))] \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes the expectation operation, $P_{data}(x)$ is the distribution of the real data, $P_G(x)$ is the distribution of the generated samples, $D(\cdot)$ denotes the discriminator function, x_r denotes a batch from the real sample, and x_G denotes a batch from the generated sample. The generation samples are come from the generator:

$$x_G = G(z) \quad (2)$$

where z is a random vector as the input of the generator, $G(\cdot)$ denotes the generator function.

The goal of the generator is trying to generate the samples that will be judged true by the discriminator, i.e. to minimize the loss function shown in equation (3):

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathbb{E}_{x_G \sim P_G(x)} [\log (1 - D(x_G))] \quad (3)$$

In summary, both of the generator and the discriminator attempt to outwit each other, and this gamble can be described as a min-max problem.

B. Developed dual-discriminator GAN

In order to investigate proper structure of GAN for better representation of EEG signal in both of the time and frequency domains, a generative adversarial network with dual-discriminator is developed. The overall framework is illustrated in Fig.2. The developments of dual-discriminator GAN comparing with the traditional GAN is described as following. Specifically, the generator takes random noise as the input and outputs the fake EEG. On the one hand, the real EEG and the fake EEG are input into the time domain discriminator D1 as time-sequence signals. Truth or falsity is judged from the perspective of the time domain. On the other hand, the power spectrum obtained after FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) are input to the frequency domain discriminator D2 to judge truth or falsity from the perspective of frequency domain. It is worth noting that the results of the time series after FFT are of complex numbers. Here, we did not take the conventional processing way by converting the complex numbers to

real numbers by taking the absolute value. Instead, the deep complex neural network [13] is adopted to construct the frequency domain discriminator in order to maximally utilize the valid information of the complex results in terms of magnitude and phase.

Fig. 2 Structure of the developed time and frequency dual-discriminator GAN

During the model training process, the goal of the discriminator D1 is to maximize the loss function shown in equation 4:

$$\mathcal{L}_{D_1} = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim P_r} [\log D_1(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{x_g \sim P_g} [\log (1 - D_1(x_g))] \quad (4)$$

where x denotes a batch from the real sample obeying distribution P_r . x_g denotes a batch from the generated sample obeying distribution P_g . $x_g = G(z)$, z denotes random noise.

The goal of the discriminator D2 is to maximize the loss function shown in equation 5:

$$\mathcal{L}_{D_2} = \mathbb{E}_{x_{FFT} \sim P_{r_{FFT}}} [\log D_2(x_{FFT})] + \mathbb{E}_{x_{g_{FFT}} \sim P_{g_{FFT}}} [\log (1 - D_2(x_{g_{FFT}}))] \quad (5)$$

where x_{FFT} and $x_{g_{FFT}}$ denote the results of the real and generated samples after the FFT, respectively.

The goal of the generator G is to minimize the loss function shown in equation 6:

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathbb{E}_{x_g \sim P_g} [\log (1 - D_1(x_g))] + \mathbb{E}_{x_{g_{FFT}} \sim P_{g_{FFT}}} [\log (1 - D_2(x_{g_{FFT}}))] \quad (6)$$

Unlike the traditional structure of GAN, the combination with a frequency domain discriminator enables the model to distinguish between real and generated samples from a perspective of frequency domain. Compared to models designed only from the perspective of time domain, the dual-discriminator has the advantage of enhancing the mining and learning of the frequency domain information of EEG signals and alleviating the risk of frequency domain distortion of generated samples.

C. Segmentation of sleep EEG signal

In order to match the actual clinical diagnostic process, many of the current studies related to sleep staging have used 30-second segments of EEG signals. However, learning to generate realistic long sequences of EEG signals is not easy for generative models. It is easy to fall into model collapse for GANs [14] [15].

In order to reduce the learning difficulty of the model and to improve the overall diversity of the synthesized EEG signals, a segmented synthesis strategy is proposed by combining the idea of integrated learning, as shown in Fig. 3. The 30-second EEG signal is split into six 5-second subsegments. Each model learns for only one of these segments. Once the model has been trained, the generator can be made to synthesize the corresponding 5-second subsegments. The final 30-second EEG sample is obtained by splicing the segments together.

Fig. 3 EEG signal synthesis method based on a segmentation strategy

D. Detail structure description

Based on the strategy of segmented synthesis, the detail construction of the dual-discriminator GAN model is described as shown in Table 1 to Table 3. In Table 1 and Table 2, the constructed generator and time domain discriminator are composed of conventional deep convolutional networks. In Table 3, the frequency domain discriminator is composed of complex neural networks. In the generator, upsampling is implemented by using deconvolution. Considering the use of 2-based FFT, the input dimension of the frequency domain discriminator is set to 512. Here, FC denotes fully connected, Conv denotes convolution, BN denotes batch normalization, MP denotes max pooling, ReLU, Tanh and Sigmoid are all activation functions. Operations with the "complex-" prefix indicate related computations involving complex numbers.

Table.1 Structure of the generator

Layer	Operation	Dimension
input	/	100
1	FC	32000
2	Reshape	256@125
3	Upsampling	256@250
4-7	Conv1×5, BN, ReLu	16@250
8	Upsampling	16@500
9	Conv1×1, BN, Tanh	1@500
output	/	500

Table.2 Structure of the time domain discriminator

Layer	Operation	Dimension
input	/	500
1-4	Conv1×3, BN, MP1×2, ReLU	128@31
5	FC	3968
6	FC	64
7	FC	1
8	Sigmoid	1
output	/	1

Table.3 Structure of the frequency domain discriminator

Layer	Operation	Dimension
input	/	512
1-4	Complex-Conv1×3, Complex-BN, Complex-Conv1×1, Complex-ReLU	128@32
5	Complex-FC	4096
6	Complex-FC	64
7	Complex-FC	1
8	Abs, Sigmoid	1
output	/	1

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the number of samples in W, N1, N2, N3 and REM stages, N2 is obviously larger than the others four stages. In order to overcome the effect of data problems for sleep staging, the time-frequency dual discriminator GAN is trained for four types of minority samples, i.e., W, N1, N3, and REM, respectively.

In this section, the experimental environment and the hyperparameter settings are described, the clinical data

set utilized for evaluation is introduced. The ablation experiments are conducted to evaluate the validity of the main improvements of proposed GAN. Moreover, the time series and the corresponding power spectrum of the generated EEG sample are given and analyzed. Finally, the generated EEG samples are applied to automatic sleep staging. The impact on performance before and after data augmentation is verified.

A. Experiment Preparation

The experimental environment uses Pytorch as the deep learning framework, and hardware is Quadra P2200 for GPU and Inter(R) Xeon(R) W-2123 CPU@3.60 GHz. During the training process, 64 samples are taken as a mini-batch and the training round is set to 3000. The number of training of generator and discriminators in each training round is 1:1. The learning rate is 0.0001 for generator and time-domain discriminator, 0.0003 for frequency-domain discriminator. SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) is used as the optimizer.

MMD (Maximum Mean Discrepancy) [16], FDWD (Frequency Domain Wasserstein Distance) and FID (Frechet Inception Distance) [17] are used as evaluation metrics to quantify the model performance, where FDWD denotes the calculation of the WD (Wasserstein distance) [18] between the real and generated signals over the frequency-domain distribution. The smaller these three metrics are, the higher the similarity between synthesized and real signals, reflecting the better performance of the model.

B. Data set description

The data set contains six subjects recorded in the hospital. Sleep stages of W, N1, N2, N3 and REM are inspected for every 30-second epoch by specialist physicians according to AASM criteria. The EEG signals recorded from the C3-M2 channel are chosen for analysis.

The sampling rate of the original signals is reduced from 256 Hz to 100 Hz. The data length LEN of each sample epoch is $100\text{ Hz} * 30s = 3000$. Normalization is performed so that the amplitude range of the signals is standardized between $[-1,1] \mu V$. In addition, the data are screened to exclude samples that are heavily contaminated by noise due to the subject's body movement or poor electrode contact.

C. Ablation experiments

In order to evaluate the quality of the proposed model, the results of G4 (corresponding to one 5-second

segment within an epoch) are analyzed in detail by calculating the three indicators.

The models are described as follows:

- ✧ Baseline: traditional GAN with only one discriminator of (real number) neural network.
- ✧ Model A: GAN with two discriminators but both are (real number) neural networks similar to the approach in [19], i.e. the result after the FFT is converted to real numbers by taking the absolute value and then used as input to the frequency domain discriminator.
- ✧ Model B: our proposed GAN with one discriminator of (real number) neural network and one discriminator of (complex number) neural network.

The results are shown in Table.4 to Table.7. The best indicators are bolded. From the results, it can be seen that our proposed model shows the best performance in almost all three metrics.

Table.4 Evaluation of 5-second segment EEG signal by G4 for stage W

	MMD	FDWD	FID
Baseline	0.0286±0.0016	0.0447±0.0003	15.4831
A	0.0207±0.0008	0.0443±0.0002	13.0604
B	0.0227±0.0010	0.0435±0.0002	12.7462

Table.5 Evaluation of 5-second segment EEG signal by G4 for stage N1

	MMD	FDWD	FID
Baseline	0.0341±0.0018	0.0477±0.0004	11.0946
A	0.0410±0.0018	0.0492±0.0002	16.8063
B	0.0258±0.0010	0.0437±0.0002	10.6508

Table.6 Evaluation of 5-second segment EEG signal by G4 for stage N3

	MMD	FDWD	FID
Baseline	0.0142±0.0007	0.0151±0.0000	6.4868
A	0.0182±0.0007	0.0151±0.0001	7.0570
B	0.0128±0.0004	0.0148±0.0001	4.8251

Table.7 Evaluation of 5-second segment EEG signal by G4 for stage REM

	MMD	FDWD	FID
Baseline	0.0226±0.0006	0.0356±0.0004	5.7309
A	0.0288±0.0004	0.0362±0.0004	5.5412
B	0.0213±0.0004	0.0354±0.0003	4.7400

D. Waveform visualization

The time series and the corresponding power spectrum of the real EEG signals (red) and the generated samples (blue) are shown in Fig. 4. For each sleep stage, the amplitude and the amount of characteristic waveforms in the power spectrum of the generated signal is similar to the real signal.

Fig. 4 Time series and power spectrum of the generated samples (blue) compared to real samples (red). (a) W (b) N1 (c) N3 (d) REM.

Specifically, for stage W, distinct α activity can be observed in the generated samples of Fig. 4(a). The corresponding power spectrum is concentrated among the range of 8-13 Hz. For stage N1, the frequency components within 4-7 Hz can be found in the time and frequency domains as shown in Fig. 4(b). For stage N3, clear slow wave components are appeared in the time series of Fig. 4(c), and the amount of 0.5-4 Hz is obvious in the power spectrum. For stage REM, there is appearance of triangular-shaped sawtooth waves in Fig. 4(d), mainly concentrated among the range of 4-7 Hz. The above phenomena are consistent with the AASM description of the EEG signal characteristics in different sleep stages.

E. Automatic sleep staging

Moreover, the classification performance of Random Forest (RF) is evaluated on sleep staging where the developed time-frequency dual discriminator GAN is applied. Experiments are executed on six subjects using leave-one-out cross-validation. All of the generated samples appear only in the training set to ensure no leakage to the validation and test sets. The RF classifier refers to the method in literature [21] and uses manually extracted features as input. In terms of parameter settings, the number of decision trees in the RF model is set to 50, and the criterion used for splitting the nodes is entropy.

The classification performance of sleep staging is evaluated by precision (PR), recall (RE), F1-score (F1) and total accuracy. The results are shown in Table.8. It can be seen that most of the metrics have been improved. Although some are slightly decreased but is also equivalent. According to Table 8, the total sleep stage classification accuracy is about 3.6%. The improvement in the performance of the classifier after using the EEG balanced training dataset synthesized by our developed model is effective for sleep staging on real clinical data.

Table.8 Sleep staging performance of RF before and after data balancing by EEG signal synthesis based on time-frequency dual discriminator GAN

	Imbalanced			Balanced		
	PR	RE	F1	PR	RE	F1
W	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.89	0.91	0.90
N1	0.33	0.29	0.31	0.37	0.35	0.36
N2	0.71	0.81	0.76	0.78	0.77	0.78
N3	0.73	0.69	0.71	0.78	0.78	0.78
REM	0.73	0.61	0.66	0.71	0.73	0.72

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a GAN with time-frequency dual discriminator structure is developed for synthesizing sleep EEG signals. The developed GAN is used in a sleep staging task dealing with the affect by data insufficient and imbalance problems for real clinical application. Compared with the traditional structure, the added frequency domain discriminator can further capture the information in the frequency domain of sleep EEG signal. The frequency domain discriminator is constructed by complex neural networks, thus being able to accept complex numbers as inputs. In addition, a segmented synthesis strategy is designed to improve the quality and diversity of the synthesized EEG.

Experimental results show that the improved model outperforms the baseline model in three evaluation metrics. The waveforms of the synthetic EEG in both time and frequency domains conform to the features that should be theoretically available. Finally, the synthetic signals are applied to the training of the random forest classifier. The results show that it can effectively improve the classification performance on sleep staging, which is effective and useful for solving the data problem of the automatic sleep staging model.

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